

Supplementary Materials

Subseasonal Temperature Forecast Refinement via Multisource Atmospheric Factor Fusion and Terrain-Aware Token-KAN

S1 Regional Definitions

To evaluate the model performance across diverse climatic and topographic regimes, mainland China is divided into eight representative subregions. These divisions are defined based on significant geographic boundaries (e.g., the Tibetan Plateau) and established climatological characteristics. Table S1 summarizes the abbreviations and specific latitude/longitude extents for each region used in the diagnostic analysis.

Table S1: Geographic boundaries of the eight subregions over mainland China.

Subregion	Abbreviation	Latitude Range	Longitude Range
Northeast	NE	39°N – 54°N	119°E – 134°E
North China	NC	36°N – 46°N	111°E – 119°E
East China	EC	27°N – 36°N	116°E – 122°E
Central China	CC	27°N – 36°N	106°E – 116°E
South China	SC	20°N – 27°N	106°E – 120°E
Tibetan Plateau	TP	27°N – 36°N	77°E – 106°E
Southwest	SW	22°N – 27°N	98°E – 106°E
Northwest	NW	36°N – 46°N	75°E – 111°E

S2 SSU: Multisource Fusion and Learnable Sub-Pixel Upsampling

S2.1 Notation and channel projection

For brevity, we omit the initialization-time index t and denote the multisource predictor tensor by $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{C \times H \times W}$. In our setting, $(H, W) = (32, 48)$. The high-resolution elevation field (aligned to the CN05.1 grid) is denoted by $\mathbf{E} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times H' \times W'}$ with $(H', W') = (192, 288)$, corresponding to an overall $\times 6$ spatial refinement.

We first compress and align the heterogeneous channel stack using a lightweight learnable projection:

$$\mathbf{Z}_0 = \phi(\mathbf{X}) \in \mathbb{R}^{C_0 \times H \times W}, \quad (\text{S1})$$

where $\phi(\cdot)$ is implemented as a small convolutional block (e.g., Conv–Norm–Activation), and C_0 is the latent width.

S2.2 PixelShuffle cascade ($\times 2 \rightarrow \times 3$)

To perform spatial refinement (i.e., preliminary statistical downscaling) before the encoder, we employ a learnable sub-pixel upsampling module (SSU) based on PixelShuffle. This design is fully learnable while avoiding the checkerboard artifacts commonly observed in transposed convolutions, and it ensures that subsequent modules operate on a grid consistent with the observation domain.

Given an integer scale factor $r \in \mathbb{N}$, PixelShuffle $PS_r(\cdot)$ reshapes

$$PS_r : \mathbb{R}^{(C \cdot r^2) \times H \times W} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{C \times (rH) \times (rW)}, \quad (\text{S2})$$

with the element-wise mapping

$$PS_r(\mathbf{Z})_{c,i,j} = \mathbf{Z}_{c \cdot r^2 + \text{mod}(i,r) \cdot r + \text{mod}(j,r), \lfloor i/r \rfloor, \lfloor j/r \rfloor}, \quad (\text{S3})$$

where c indexes output channels and (i, j) indexes output spatial locations.

STA-UKAN adopts a two-stage cascade ($\times 2 \rightarrow \times 3$) to achieve the total $\times 6$ refinement:

$$\mathbf{Z}_2 = PS_2(\phi_2(\mathbf{Z}_0)), \quad \mathbf{Z}_6 = PS_3(\phi_3(\mathbf{Z}_2)), \quad (\text{S4})$$

where ϕ_2 and ϕ_3 are learnable 3×3 convolutions that expand channels to satisfy the PixelShuffle constraints:

$$\phi_2 : \mathbb{R}^{C_0 \times H \times W} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{(C_0 \cdot 2^2) \times H \times W}, \quad (\text{S5})$$

$$\phi_3 : \mathbb{R}^{C_0 \times 2H \times 2W} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{(C_0 \cdot 3^2) \times 2H \times 2W}. \quad (\text{S6})$$

The resulting high-resolution feature map $\mathbf{Z}_6 \in \mathbb{R}^{C_0 \times H' \times W'}$ is fed into the terrain-aware encoder described in the main text.

Design note. The progressive $\times 2 \rightarrow \times 3$ cascade is adopted for training stability and empirical performance under our $(32, 48) \rightarrow (192, 288)$ setting. Other upsampling operators (e.g., bilinear interpolation or transposed convolutions) can be evaluated under the same protocol.

S3 MAFF encoder: Terrain-Guided Multiscale Encoding

S3.1 Multiscale elevation pyramid and injection

To capture the impact of complex topography on meteorological variable distributions, we construct a multiscale elevation pyramid from the high-resolution elevation field $\mathbf{E} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times H' \times W'}$. At encoder stage s with spatial resolution (H_s, W_s) , we obtain the matched-resolution elevation map via bilinear interpolation:

$$\mathbf{E}_s = \mathcal{B}_s(\mathbf{E}) \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times H_s \times W_s}. \quad (\text{S7})$$

Let $\mathbf{F}_s \in \mathbb{R}^{C_s \times H_s \times W_s}$ denote the atmospheric feature map entering stage s . Elevation is injected by channel concatenation:

$$\mathbf{G}_s = \text{Concat}(\mathbf{F}_s, \mathbf{E}_s) \in \mathbb{R}^{(C_s+1) \times H_s \times W_s}. \quad (\text{S8})$$

S3.2 Multi-branch extraction, fusion, and SE reweighting

At stage s , MAFF applies parallel convolution branches with kernel sizes $k \in \{3, 5, 7\}$:

$$\mathbf{U}_s^k = \sigma\left(\text{BN}\left(\mathbf{W}_s^k * \mathbf{G}_s\right)\right), \quad k \in \{3, 5, 7\}, \quad (\text{S9})$$

where $*$ denotes convolution, BN denotes batch normalization, and $\sigma(\cdot)$ is ReLU. Branch features are fused by concatenation followed by a 1×1 convolution:

$$\mathbf{V}_s = \psi\left(\text{Concat}(\mathbf{U}_s^3, \mathbf{U}_s^5, \mathbf{U}_s^7)\right) \in \mathbb{R}^{C_s \times H_s \times W_s}, \quad (\text{S10})$$

where $\psi(\cdot)$ is a 1×1 convolution for channel mixing and compression.

We then apply squeeze-and-excitation (SE) style channel reweighting. Let $\text{GAP}(\cdot)$ denote global average pooling and $\delta(\cdot)$ denote ReLU. The channel weights are computed by a two-layer MLP:

$$\mathbf{a}_s = \text{Sigmoid}(\mathbf{W}_2 \delta(\mathbf{W}_1 \text{GAP}(\mathbf{V}_s))) \in \mathbb{R}^{C_s}. \quad (\text{S11})$$

The reweighted feature map is

$$\tilde{\mathbf{V}}_s = \mathbf{a}_s \odot \mathbf{V}_s, \quad (\text{S12})$$

where \odot denotes channel-wise multiplication (with broadcasting).

S3.3 Residual projection and stage output

Finally, we add a residual projection of the stage input for stable optimization:

$$\mathbf{S}_s = \text{ReLU}(\tilde{\mathbf{V}}_s + \mathbf{P}_s(\mathbf{F}_s)) \in \mathbb{R}^{C_s \times H_s \times W_s}, \quad (\text{S13})$$

where \mathbf{P}_s is a 1×1 convolution used to match channel dimensions. \mathbf{S}_s is forwarded to the next encoder stage and stored as the skip feature for the decoder.

Table S2: Tokenization hyperparameters for the Token-KAN bottleneck.

Hyperparameter	Value
Patch size	3×3
Stride	2
Overlap	1
Embedding dim D	see Table S3 (varies by stage)
Token-KAN stages	4 (2 encoder + 2 decoder)

S4 Token-KAN: Tokenized Nonlinear Modeling and Reconstruction

S4.1 Tokenization (OverlapPatchEmbed)

Let $\mathbf{F}_{\text{bn}} \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times C_b \times H_b \times W_b}$ denote the bottleneck feature map produced by the encoder (after MAFF stages). An overlap patch embedding (OverlapPatchEmbed) converts it to a token sequence:

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{tok}} = \text{Tokenize}(\mathbf{F}_{\text{bn}}) \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times N \times D}, \quad (\text{S14})$$

where B is batch size, N is the number of tokens, and D is the token embedding dimension.

S4.2 KANLinear parameterization

Token-KAN replaces standard linear transformations with learnable 1D nonlinear functions, inspired by the Kolmogorov–Arnold representation. Given $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}}$, a KANLinear layer maps it to $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{out}}}$ by

$$y_j = \sum_{i=1}^{d_{\text{in}}} \phi_{j,i}(x_i), \quad j = 1, \dots, d_{\text{out}}, \quad (\text{S15})$$

where each $\phi_{j,i}(\cdot)$ is a learnable scalar-to-scalar function. In our implementation, $\phi_{j,i}$ is parameterized as

$$\phi_{j,i}(x) = a_{j,i} + \sum_{m=1}^M b_{j,i,m} \sigma(x - c_{j,i,m})^\gamma, \quad (\text{S16})$$

where $\sigma(\cdot)$ is SiLU, $a_{j,i}$, $b_{j,i,m}$, $c_{j,i,m}$ are learnable parameters, M is the number of basis components, and γ controls the shape (fixed or learnable depending on Table S2). This parameterization yields variable-wise nonlinear response curves that can be inspected after training.

S4.3 Token-KAN block

To enhance spatial structural modeling and training stability, each Token-KAN block couples KANLinear with depthwise convolution (DwConv) and layer normalization (LayerNorm). Given tokens \mathbf{X}_{tok} , a block computes

$$\mathbf{H}_1 = \text{KANLinear}(\mathbf{X}_{\text{tok}}), \quad (\text{S17})$$

$$\mathbf{H}_2 = \text{DwConv}(\mathbf{H}_1), \quad (\text{S18})$$

$$\mathbf{Z}_{\text{tok}} = \text{LayerNorm}(\mathbf{H}_2), \quad (\text{S19})$$

where DwConv operates on the reshaped token grid (implementation details follow Table S2).

S4.4 Decoder: progressive PixelShuffle with skip and elevation fusion

After Token-KAN processing, tokens are reshaped back to a spatial feature map:

$$\mathbf{D}_L = \text{Reshape}(\mathbf{Z}_{\text{tok}}) \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times C_L \times H_L \times W_L}, \quad (\text{S20})$$

where (H_L, W_L) is the bottleneck spatial size and L indexes the coarsest decoder level.

We use a 5-stage PixelShuffle decoder, where each stage performs $\times 2$ upsampling and fuses (i) the corresponding encoder skip feature and (ii) the matched-resolution elevation map. At

Table S3: Detailed layer configuration of the STA-UKAN network.

Module	Operation	Kernel	In/Out ch.	Output size ($H \times W$)
0) Input projection				
Projection layer	Linear projection to unified feature space (identity if already projected)	1×1	C_{in}/C_0	32×48
1) SSU front-end (Stepwise Sub-pixel Upsampling)				
SSU	PixelShuffle cascade ($\times 2 \rightarrow \times 3$, total $\times 6$)	3×3	C_0/C_0	192×288
2) MAFF encoder (Multivariate Atmospheric Factors Fusion)				
MAFF Stage 1	Multi-branch Conv(3, 5, 7) \rightarrow Cat $\rightarrow 1 \times 1$ Conv \rightarrow SE \rightarrow Residual \rightarrow MaxPool(2)	3/5/7	$C_0/32$	96×144
Terrain injection	Bilinear resize(topography) and inject as an extra channel	-	$32 \rightarrow (32 + 1)$	96×144
MAFF Stage 2	Multi-branch Conv(3, 5, 7) \rightarrow Cat $\rightarrow 1 \times 1$ Conv \rightarrow SE \rightarrow Residual \rightarrow MaxPool(2)	3/5/7	$(32 + 1)/64$	48×72
Terrain injection	Bilinear resize(topography) and inject as an extra channel	-	$64 \rightarrow (64 + 1)$	48×72
MAFF Stage 3	Multi-branch Conv(3, 5, 7) \rightarrow Cat $\rightarrow 1 \times 1$ Conv \rightarrow SE \rightarrow Residual \rightarrow MaxPool(2)	3/5/7	$(64 + 1)/128$	24×36
Terrain injection	Bilinear resize(topography) and inject as an extra channel	-	$128 \rightarrow (128 + 1)$	24×36
3) Token-KAN bottleneck (Tokenized KAN)				
Token-KAN Enc. 1	OverlapPatchEmbed (stride 2) \rightarrow Token-KAN (KANBlock)	3×3	$(128 + 1)/256$	12×18
Token-KAN Enc. 2	OverlapPatchEmbed (stride 2) \rightarrow Token-KAN (KANBlock)	3×3	$(256 + 1)/512$	6×9
4) Decoder (SSU decoder + Token-KAN decoder, with skip connections)				
Dec. 1 (SSU decoder)	Sub-pixel upsampling (Conv \rightarrow PixelShuffle $\times 2$) + Skip-add	3×3	$(512 + 1)/256$	12×18
Token-KAN Dec. 1	Token-KAN refinement (KANBlock)	-	$256/256$	12×18
Dec. 2 (SSU decoder)	Sub-pixel upsampling (Conv \rightarrow PixelShuffle $\times 2$) + Skip-add	3×3	$256/128$	24×36
Token-KAN Dec. 2	Token-KAN refinement (KANBlock)	-	$128/128$	24×36
Dec. 3 (SSU decoder)	Sub-pixel upsampling (Conv \rightarrow PixelShuffle $\times 2$) + Skip-add	3×3	$128/64$	48×72
Dec. 4 (SSU decoder)	Sub-pixel upsampling (Conv \rightarrow PixelShuffle $\times 2$) + Skip-add	3×3	$64/32$	96×144
Dec. 5 (SSU decoder)	Sub-pixel upsampling (Conv \rightarrow PixelShuffle $\times 2$)	3×3	$32/32$	192×288
Final	Conv2d	1×1	$32/1$	192×288

decoder stage $\ell \in \{L, L-1, \dots, L-4\}$, let $\mathbf{S}_\ell \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times C_\ell \times H_\ell \times W_\ell}$ denote the skip feature from the encoder, and let

$$\mathbf{E}_\ell = \mathcal{B}_\ell(\mathbf{E}) \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times 1 \times H_\ell \times W_\ell} \quad (\text{S21})$$

be the elevation map resized to the same resolution.

We first concatenate the decoder state, skip, and elevation, and then apply a learnable channel-expansion convolution before PixelShuffle to satisfy the r^2 constraint:

$$\mathbf{Q}_\ell = \text{Concat}(\mathbf{D}_\ell, \mathbf{S}_\ell, \mathbf{E}_\ell), \quad (\text{S22})$$

$$\mathbf{R}_\ell = \phi_\ell^{\text{dec}}(\mathbf{Q}_\ell) \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times (4C_{\ell-1}) \times H_\ell \times W_\ell}, \quad (\text{S23})$$

$$\mathbf{D}_{\ell-1} = \text{PS}_2(\mathbf{R}_\ell) \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times C_{\ell-1} \times (2H_\ell) \times (2W_\ell)}, \quad (\text{S24})$$

where ϕ_ℓ^{dec} is typically a 3×3 convolution producing $4C_{\ell-1}$ channels so that PixelShuffle with $r = 2$ outputs $C_{\ell-1}$ channels.

After the final upsampling stage, a 1×1 convolution projects the features to the target variable:

$$\hat{\mathbf{Y}} = \text{Conv}_{1 \times 1}(\mathbf{D}_{L-5}) \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times 1 \times 192 \times 288}, \quad (\text{S25})$$

yielding the refined, downscaled weekly-mean 2-m temperature field on the CN05.1 grid.

S5 Network configuration

Table S3 details the layer-wise configuration of STA-UKAN, corresponding to the specific modules (SSU, MAFF, and Token-KAN) defined in Figure 2 of the main text. Channel increases denoted as “+1” are caused by terrain injection, where the high-resolution topography is resized by bilinear interpolation to each stage and appended as an additional channel (implementation uses dummy-channel replacement, which is equivalent to concatenation).

S6 Training protocol and reproducibility

S6.1 Chronological split

All experiments follow the same strictly chronological protocol used in the main text: 2006–2019 for training, 2020 for validation, and 2021–2022 for independent testing. This split is applied consistently to STA-UKAN and to all learning-based baselines unless otherwise noted. A separate model is trained for each lead week so that lead-dependent error characteristics are learned explicitly rather than averaged across Weeks 2–5.

S6.2 Optimization and regularization

STA-UKAN is optimized with Adam using $\beta = (0.9, 0.999)$ and a cosine-annealing learning-rate schedule. We apply weight decay of 1×10^{-4} , early stopping with a patience of 10 epochs, and a maximum training budget of 50 epochs. The initial learning rate is 5×10^{-3} , and the loss function is the Charbonnier loss with $\varepsilon = 10^{-3}$, consistent with the main-text protocol.

S6.3 Determinism

We fix the random seed to 42 and enable deterministic operators whenever supported by the backend. Minor numerical variation may still occur across different CUDA/cuDNN versions, driver stacks, and hardware platforms; however, such effects do not alter the qualitative conclusions reported in this study.

Table S4: Training hyperparameters and reproducibility settings.

Item	Value
Optimizer	Adam ($\beta_1 = 0.9, \beta_2 = 0.999$)
Learning rate	5×10^{-3} (initial)
Scheduler	CosineAnnealingLR
Weight decay	1×10^{-4}
Early stopping	patience = 10
Max epochs	50
Loss	Charbonnier, $\varepsilon = 10^{-3}$
Seed	42
Determinism	deterministic ops enabled when available

S7 Baseline comparison across lead times (Weeks 2–5)

Implementation notes and fair-comparison protocol. We distinguish two CMA reference baselines throughout the manuscript. **CMA_cf** denotes the interpolated *control forecast* (CF) member only, whereas **CMA_interp** denotes the interpolated *ensemble mean* obtained by averaging the control and perturbed members on the native CMA grid before interpolation to the CN05.1 target grid. Unless otherwise stated, **CMA_cf** is used as the primary raw-reference forecast in the main text, while **CMA_interp** is retained as a more stable ensemble-mean reference in the supplementary comparison.

All learning-based baselines use the same chronological training/validation/test split as STA-UKAN and are tuned without access to test information. For computational feasibility, the statistical and classical machine-learning baselines are trained using temperature-related predictors only, whereas the deep-learning baselines and STA-UKAN use the full multisource predictor stack described in the main text. To control for the effect of input-feature richness, we additionally report a *temperature-only sensitivity experiment for STA-UKAN itself* in Section S11. This supplementary analysis is intended to evaluate the sensitivity of the proposed framework to restricted predictor sets; it is *not* part of the formal 22-method baseline list.

For deep-learning competitors (U-Net, EDSR, SwinIR, and STA-UKAN), we first carried out a coarse search to identify reasonable optimization ranges and then performed a structured validation-based search over learning rate, weight decay, and cosine-annealing period T_{\max} . The configuration with the best validation performance was selected once and evaluated once on the held-out 2021–2022 test period.

Table S5: Baseline comparison across lead times (Weeks 2–5) with inline 95% confidence intervals. Lower is better for MAE and RMSE.

Model	MAE↓ (95% CI)	RMSE↓ (95% CI)	MBE	ACC↑	PCC↑	p-value
Lead Week 2						
CMA_cf	2.435 (2.386–2.492)	3.147 (3.083–3.222)	0.027	0.398	0.941	–
EC_cf	2.393 (2.339–2.453)	3.203 (3.128–3.279)	-0.572	0.398	0.943	2.32e-01
CMA_interp	2.359 (2.315–2.409)	3.050 (2.992–3.114)	0.034	0.411	0.944	2.90e-17
EC_interp	2.243 (2.194–2.293)	3.031 (2.966–3.098)	-0.668	0.397	0.948	8.57e-04
EC_CMA_interp	2.124 (2.083–2.170)	2.829 (2.774–2.890)	-0.481	0.427	0.953	7.81e-25
QM	2.111 (2.071–2.157)	2.773 (2.721–2.832)	-0.317	0.438	0.954	9.58e-49
QDM	2.033 (2.001–2.067)	2.938 (2.897–2.984)	-0.530	0.342	0.941	1.01e-08
RF	1.533 (1.481–1.588)	1.968 (1.900–2.038)	-0.151	0.435	0.984	3.05e-111
GBR	1.341 (1.300–1.388)	1.760 (1.698–1.823)	-0.073	0.598	0.983	4.95e-136

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Table S5: Baseline comparison across lead times (Weeks 2–5) with inline 95% confidence intervals (continued).

Model	MAE↓ (95% CI)	RMSE↓ (95% CI)	MBE	ACC↑	PCC↑	p-value
SGDRegressor	1.342 (1.298–1.390)	1.754 (1.692–1.817)	-0.051	0.617	0.984	1.43e-138
AdaBoost	1.441 (1.402–1.484)	1.866 (1.812–1.923)	-0.142	0.498	0.982	4.00e-127
LightGBM	1.332 (1.292–1.378)	1.745 (1.685–1.808)	-0.071	0.604	0.984	2.05e-136
SVM	1.289 (1.248–1.335)	1.687 (1.626–1.749)	-0.063	0.625	0.985	4.69e-142
XGBoost	1.340 (1.299–1.386)	1.756 (1.696–1.819)	-0.070	0.598	0.983	1.65e-135
UNET	1.310 (1.268–1.351)	1.701 (1.645–1.759)	-0.572	0.564	0.986	2.13e-130
C.UNET	1.228 (1.185–1.271)	1.599 (1.538–1.660)	-0.322	0.629	0.987	4.08e-146
EDSR	1.283 (1.248–1.321)	1.656 (1.605–1.706)	-0.339	0.586	0.986	2.53e-137
SWINIR	1.283 (1.242–1.326)	1.668 (1.611–1.727)	-0.288	0.612	0.985	2.05e-144
RCAN	1.293 (1.253–1.334)	1.683 (1.628–1.741)	-0.127	0.583	0.985	8.22e-137
SRCNN	1.392 (1.356–1.430)	1.797 (1.745–1.849)	-0.265	0.547	0.981	1.28e-135
SRRESNET	1.359 (1.316–1.403)	1.749 (1.687–1.807)	-0.578	0.574	0.985	1.00e-132
SRDRN	1.274 (1.236–1.316)	1.649 (1.595–1.705)	-0.093	0.601	0.986	2.33e-146
STA_UKAN	1.217 (1.178–1.255)	1.586 (1.529–1.641)	-0.303	0.635	0.987	3.27e-145
Lead Week 3						
CMA_cf	2.970 (2.892–3.056)	3.806 (3.708–3.916)	0.435	0.193	0.923	–
EC_cf	2.809 (2.733–2.882)	3.658 (3.561–3.753)	-0.717	0.209	0.930	1.66e-02
CMA_interp	2.670 (2.608–2.744)	3.426 (3.351–3.512)	0.406	0.214	0.934	5.94e-28
EC_interp	2.477 (2.415–2.536)	3.228 (3.155–3.305)	-0.738	0.200	0.944	4.55e-24
EC_CMA_interp	2.368 (2.313–2.426)	3.062 (2.994–3.133)	-0.433	0.227	0.947	4.24e-47
QM	2.366 (2.314–2.425)	3.048 (2.983–3.118)	-0.166	0.236	0.946	2.99e-60
QDM	2.307 (2.255–2.360)	3.204 (3.146–3.260)	-0.467	0.149	0.934	2.55e-30

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Table S5: Baseline comparison across lead times (Weeks 2–5) with inline 95% confidence intervals (continued).

Model	MAE↓ (95% CI)	RMSE↓ (95% CI)	MBE	ACC↑	PCC↑	p-value
RF	1.809 (1.755–1.868)	2.329 (2.258–2.403)	-0.174	0.199	0.973	2.21e-98
GBR	1.691 (1.629–1.753)	2.195 (2.114–2.276)	-0.059	0.321	0.975	1.22e-111
SGDRegressor	1.702 (1.640–1.767)	2.196 (2.114–2.280)	-0.050	0.350	0.975	1.36e-113
AdaBoost	1.754 (1.698–1.814)	2.261 (2.188–2.335)	-0.143	0.247	0.974	2.66e-104
LightGBM	1.682 (1.621–1.745)	2.184 (2.103–2.265)	-0.058	0.326	0.975	5.62e-112
SVM	1.639 (1.582–1.696)	2.121 (2.044–2.197)	-0.112	0.333	0.977	1.64e-114
XGBoost	1.688 (1.627–1.748)	2.190 (2.111–2.270)	-0.056	0.321	0.975	1.85e-111
UNET	1.633 (1.576–1.691)	2.121 (2.043–2.199)	-0.157	0.287	0.977	1.44e-110
C.UNET	1.715 (1.654–1.783)	2.223 (2.140–2.313)	-0.550	0.187	0.977	1.48e-97
EDSR	1.720 (1.655–1.787)	2.239 (2.154–2.330)	-0.460	0.242	0.976	1.59e-97
SWINIR	1.648 (1.588–1.709)	2.146 (2.067–2.229)	-0.127	0.304	0.977	6.86e-109
RCAN	1.741 (1.683–1.804)	2.262 (2.182–2.347)	-0.112	0.260	0.973	4.73e-104
SRCNN	1.781 (1.723–1.840)	2.297 (2.220–2.372)	-0.351	0.242	0.972	4.25e-102
SRRESNET	1.707 (1.644–1.776)	2.235 (2.146–2.328)	-0.358	0.239	0.975	2.30e-99
SRDRN	1.692 (1.635–1.753)	2.188 (2.109–2.268)	-0.528	0.227	0.977	1.21e-101
STA_UKAN	1.587 (1.528–1.647)	2.061 (1.982–2.138)	-0.069	0.363	0.979	5.23e-118
Lead Week 4						
CMA_cf	3.083 (2.999–3.173)	3.955 (3.844–4.065)	0.512	0.128	0.917	–
EC_cf	2.952 (2.858–3.041)	3.823 (3.701–3.934)	-0.720	0.127	0.926	2.00e-02
CMA_interp	2.675 (2.604–2.749)	3.444 (3.354–3.529)	0.555	0.165	0.934	4.48e-29
EC_interp	2.562 (2.487–2.635)	3.319 (3.228–3.409)	-0.788	0.103	0.942	1.12e-26
EC_CMA_interp	2.433 (2.366–2.502)	3.140 (3.058–3.223)	-0.430	0.135	0.945	5.84e-47

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Table S5: Baseline comparison across lead times (Weeks 2–5) with inline 95% confidence intervals (continued).

Model	MAE↓ (95% CI)	RMSE↓ (95% CI)	MBE	ACC↑	PCC↑	p-value
QM	2.413 (2.346–2.478)	3.110 (3.029–3.187)	-0.117	0.155	0.945	3.00e-56
QDM	2.362 (2.307–2.416)	3.259 (3.196–3.320)	-0.456	0.066	0.932	2.37e-31
RF	1.944 (1.873–2.014)	2.505 (2.418–2.595)	-0.202	0.045	0.970	5.97e-83
GBR	1.808 (1.739–1.875)	2.349 (2.261–2.439)	-0.091	0.160	0.972	1.50e-97
SGDRegressor	1.802 (1.733–1.866)	2.327 (2.237–2.413)	-0.068	0.209	0.973	7.29e-101
AdaBoost	1.876 (1.808–1.945)	2.430 (2.339–2.522)	-0.187	0.098	0.972	3.69e-91
LightGBM	1.800 (1.730–1.866)	2.338 (2.246–2.425)	-0.091	0.164	0.973	3.85e-98
SVM	1.750 (1.678–1.819)	2.269 (2.178–2.362)	-0.162	0.163	0.975	1.16e-100
XGBoost	1.806 (1.737–1.872)	2.347 (2.255–2.437)	-0.091	0.160	0.972	1.01e-97
UNET	1.830 (1.754–1.903)	2.418 (2.308–2.516)	-0.334	0.032	0.973	1.34e-85
C.UNET	1.808 (1.735–1.887)	2.364 (2.262–2.470)	-0.472	0.087	0.974	1.57e-88
EDSR	1.803 (1.732–1.878)	2.344 (2.249–2.440)	-0.414	0.114	0.974	3.00e-89
SWINIR	1.834 (1.753–1.910)	2.397 (2.287–2.497)	-0.298	0.112	0.974	4.20e-87
RCAN	1.867 (1.793–1.941)	2.422 (2.322–2.522)	-0.420	0.102	0.971	1.70e-88
SRCNN	1.892 (1.821–1.959)	2.456 (2.364–2.547)	-0.299	0.119	0.969	3.67e-89
SRRESNET	1.838 (1.759–1.917)	2.399 (2.293–2.504)	-0.537	0.068	0.974	2.12e-84
SRDRN	1.750 (1.674–1.821)	2.283 (2.179–2.380)	-0.320	0.164	0.975	9.72e-97
STA_UKAN	1.741 (1.668–1.811)	2.268 (2.169–2.361)	-0.349	0.165	0.976	4.90e-99
Lead Week 5						
CMA_cf	3.152 (3.061–3.248)	4.034 (3.921–4.153)	0.547	0.124	0.917	–
EC_cf	3.018 (2.911–3.124)	3.914 (3.763–4.064)	-0.748	0.080	0.923	2.10e-02
CMA_interp	2.706 (2.635–2.778)	3.472 (3.387–3.557)	0.625	0.144	0.935	5.55e-31

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Table S5: Baseline comparison across lead times (Weeks 2–5) with inline 95% confidence intervals (continued).

Model	MAE↓ (95% CI)	RMSE↓ (95% CI)	MBE	ACC↑	PCC↑	p-value
EC_interp	2.551 (2.472–2.629)	3.316 (3.213–3.417)	-0.770	0.089	0.941	1.41e-30
EC_CMA_interp	2.436 (2.363–2.511)	3.150 (3.055–3.244)	-0.398	0.118	0.945	5.88e-51
QM	2.427 (2.359–2.496)	3.129 (3.043–3.216)	-0.073	0.135	0.945	2.15e-60
QDM	2.371 (2.317–2.427)	3.264 (3.204–3.325)	-0.410	0.051	0.932	2.82e-36
RF	1.958 (1.884–2.033)	2.524 (2.421–2.622)	-0.143	0.017	0.970	2.65e-86
GBR	1.821 (1.752–1.892)	2.362 (2.268–2.453)	-0.051	0.128	0.972	6.43e-100
SGDRegressor	1.829 (1.756–1.903)	2.362 (2.254–2.458)	-0.026	0.167	0.972	2.17e-103
AdaBoost	1.896 (1.826–1.967)	2.446 (2.354–2.540)	-0.147	0.064	0.971	6.21e-93
LightGBM	1.814 (1.745–1.886)	2.352 (2.258–2.445)	-0.054	0.129	0.973	3.63e-100
SVM	1.776 (1.707–1.848)	2.298 (2.204–2.390)	-0.136	0.107	0.974	2.08e-102
XGBoost	1.819 (1.752–1.891)	2.358 (2.265–2.451)	-0.050	0.126	0.972	2.31e-100
UNET	1.833 (1.752–1.912)	2.405 (2.288–2.515)	-0.510	-0.001	0.974	3.44e-89
C_UNET	1.801 (1.726–1.877)	2.351 (2.242–2.453)	-0.176	0.123	0.973	1.75e-99
EDSR	1.815 (1.739–1.889)	2.371 (2.264–2.474)	-0.476	0.060	0.974	2.11e-91
SWINIR	1.798 (1.723–1.871)	2.338 (2.234–2.440)	-0.263	0.099	0.974	9.23e-96
RCAN	1.879 (1.806–1.953)	2.440 (2.338–2.543)	-0.422	0.004	0.971	2.31e-91
SRCNN	1.877 (1.805–1.949)	2.440 (2.339–2.540)	-0.372	0.090	0.970	1.45e-92
SRRESNET	1.834 (1.754–1.909)	2.389 (2.278–2.499)	-0.237	0.103	0.972	3.37e-94
SRDRN	1.798 (1.727–1.871)	2.342 (2.241–2.443)	-0.195	0.077	0.974	8.57e-98
STA_UKAN	1.742 (1.670–1.816)	2.274 (2.177–2.368)	-0.222	0.099	0.975	1.00e-101

Density Scatter Plot: Predicted vs Observed (Week 2-5 Combined)

Figure S1: Density scatter plots of predicted versus observed 2-m temperature aggregated over all lead times (Weeks 2–5) for (a) Bi-EnsMean, (b) SGDR regressor, (c) U-Net, and (d) STA-UKAN. The dashed line denotes perfect prediction ($y = x$).

S8 Calibration diagnostics: density scatter plots

Supplementary analysis. Figure S1 compares predicted and observed weekly-mean 2-m temperature aggregated across lead Weeks 2–5. All methods capture the overall linear relationship between forecasts and observations, but their calibration quality differs substantially. The raw bi-model ensemble mean (*Bi-EnsMean*) shows the broadest dispersion around the one-to-one line and a clear negative bias, indicating systematic underestimation over a wide temperature range. *SGDR* noticeably narrows the spread and reduces the mean bias, suggesting that even classical machine-learning-based post-processing can improve bulk calibration. *U-Net* further increases the concentration of samples near the one-to-one line, but a residual cold bias remains visible. Among the four methods, *STA-UKAN* exhibits the tightest density ridge aligned with the dashed reference line, together with the highest correlation and the lowest RMSE shown in the panels. This indicates that the proposed framework improves not only average accuracy but also the overall calibration consistency across the full temperature range. At the same time, slight residual deviations remain near the distribution tails, implying that extreme conditions are still more challenging than the central part of the distribution.

S9 Monthly PCC and temporal robustness

Supplementary analysis. Figure S2 provides a month-by-month complement to the main-text temporal robustness analysis by examining the pattern correlation coefficient (PCC) of latitude-wise weekly temperature anomalies over the 24 verification months in 2021–2022. Overall, *STA-UKAN* attains the highest or near-highest PCC in many months and yields the largest average PCC among the displayed methods, indicating that its improvements extend beyond magnitude-error reduction to better preserving the spatial structure of observed anomaly evolution. In contrast, *Bi-EnsMean* shows pronounced month-to-month variability and even negative correlations in several months, reflecting unstable representation of anomaly patterns during difficult periods. *SGDR* improves upon the raw ensemble mean in many months, but its skill remains less stable than that of the deep-learning models. *U-Net* also achieves strong correlations in a number of months, yet *STA-UKAN* is generally more consistent across both years, especially during months with comparatively low baseline skill. This behavior is consistent with the main-text temporal analysis and supports the conclusion that the proposed framework improves both temporal robustness and large-scale anomaly-structure fidelity.

Figure S2: Monthly Pattern Correlation Coefficient (PCC) over 24 months (2021–2022). Bar height denotes the correlation of latitude-wise anomalies with observations; dashed line separates 2021 and 2022.

S10 Worst-case bias robustness and computational efficiency

Figure S3: Worst-case bias robustness: aggregated MBE over the top-5 samples with the largest *Bi-EnsMean* bias at each lead week (Weeks 2–5).

Supplementary analysis. Figure S3 complements the main-text case-based analysis by focusing on the most difficult situations, namely the top-5 samples with the largest *Bi-EnsMean* bias at each lead week. In these worst-case subsets, the raw dynamical forecasts and their ensemble mean exhibit broad, spatially coherent bias structures, with pronounced cold bias over large parts of mainland China and persistent warm bias over northeastern China, especially at longer leads. This indicates that the largest forecast failures are not dominated by isolated local errors, but rather by organized large-scale bias patterns. Relative to these raw baselines,

all learning-based methods reduce the spatial extent and magnitude of the worst-case bias to some degree. Among them, *STA-UKAN* generally yields the most balanced residual pattern, with weaker large-area bias structures and more localized errors than the raw ensemble mean. Compared with *SGDRegressor* and *U-Net*, its residual bias field is overall less spatially organized, particularly in Weeks 2–3. At the same time, coherent residual cold bias remains visible in parts of central and southern China during Weeks 4–5, and some warm-side residuals persist over the far northeast. These results suggest that the proposed framework improves robustness under difficult forecast episodes, although the most extreme large-scale bias regimes are not eliminated completely.

Table S6: Computational efficiency of deep-learning baselines under the same evaluation setting (input: 192×288). Reported are parameter count (Params), compute (GMACs), latency, throughput, and peak GPU memory.

Model	Params (M)	GMACs	Latency (ms)	Throughput (samples/s)	Peak Memory (MB)
UNET	31.77	86.86	10.51	115.2	6196.7
UKAN-Interp	18.89	7.31	7.46	241.3	1935.7
UKAN-SSU	28.15	44.05	7.57	166.8	1969.9
UKAN-SSU+Topo	28.17	44.06	8.49	159.8	1971.1
STA-UKAN	29.44	81.39	16.92	69.8	2302.9
DL_EDSR	32.46	74.42	8.52	160.9	2021.9
DL_SWINIR	26.54	42.30	10.92	132.8	567.6
DL_RCAN	4.83	9.95	6.13	534.6	489.2
DL_SRCNN	0.20	2.31	0.21	8895.7	249.4
DL_SRRESNET	3.03	6.47	2.51	735.6	481.2
DL_SRDRN	1.75	5.08	2.74	330.6	908.4

Note: All efficiency metrics are measured using the same profiling script and the target input resolution (192×288). Latency and throughput may vary with hardware, precision, batch size, and implementation details.

S11 Temperature-feature configuration sensitivity of STA-UKAN

This section examines how the proposed framework behaves when its input space is progressively simplified. We compare three *temperature-only* STA-UKAN configurations—CMA Temp. only, EC Temp. only, and CMA+EC Temp. only—with the full-feature STA-UKAN model used in the main text. These variants retain the same overall architecture but remove the auxiliary atmospheric predictors and associated multivariable information; the single-source variants additionally restrict the temperature input to one forecast system only.

As shown in Table S7, combining temperature predictors from CMA and ECMWF is generally more effective than using either source alone, indicating that the two systems provide complementary temperature guidance. However, the full-feature configuration still performs best overall, especially at Weeks 3–5. This result supports the interpretation advanced in the main text: multisource temperature predictors are valuable, but the strongest performance is obtained only when auxiliary atmospheric variables and terrain-aware conditioning are retained. Importantly, these experiments are sensitivity analyses of STA-UKAN itself rather than additional baselines.

Table S7: Temperature-feature configuration sensitivity (MAE/RMSE/MBE). Lower MAE/RMSE is better; MBE closer to 0 is better.

Training Setting	2 Weeks			3 Weeks			4 Weeks			5 Weeks		
	MAE↓	RMSE↓	MBE									
CMA Temp. only	1.501	1.977	-0.493	1.727	2.247	-0.096	1.830	2.410	-0.628	1.856	2.392	-0.275
EC Temp. only	1.239	1.614	-0.243	1.618	2.121	-0.184	1.803	2.364	-0.465	1.770	2.303	-0.126
CMA+EC Temp. only	1.238	1.612	-0.377	1.681	2.170	-0.354	1.763	2.299	-0.144	1.759	2.289	-0.132
All Features (STA-UKAN)	1.217	1.586	-0.303	1.587	2.061	-0.069	1.741	2.268	-0.349	1.742	2.274	-0.222

S12 Seasonal training sensitivity

We evaluate whether season-specific training offers an advantage over a unified all-year model. Table S8 reports MAE, RMSE, and MBE across lead Weeks 2–5. Although some season-specific models perform competitively for individual lead–season combinations, the performance spread across seasons is large, and the autumn-only setting in particular becomes unstable at longer leads. This behavior suggests over-specialization when the effective training sample size is reduced. By contrast, the unified all-year STA-UKAN model yields consistently lower and more stable errors across all lead weeks and is therefore retained as the default configuration in the main manuscript.

Table S8: Season-specific training sensitivity (MAE/RMSE/MBE). Lower MAE/RMSE is better; MBE closer to 0 is better. The unified all-year model (All Features / STA-UKAN) is included for reference.

Subset	2 Weeks			3 Weeks			4 Weeks			5 Weeks		
	MAE↓	RMSE↓	MBE									
Spring	1.420	1.824	-0.702	1.551	1.996	0.243	1.560	1.981	0.142	1.494	1.905	0.432
Summer	1.041	1.332	-0.341	1.264	1.607	-0.391	1.315	1.691	0.337	1.413	1.831	0.068
Autumn	1.317	1.707	0.492	1.930	2.519	0.471	4.130	5.451	3.296	2.084	2.666	0.676
Winter	1.540	1.993	-0.187	1.949	2.492	-0.216	2.168	2.758	-0.013	2.307	2.932	-0.124
Seasonal Mean (avg.)	1.329	1.714	-0.185	1.673	2.154	0.027	2.293	2.970	0.941	1.824	2.333	0.263
All-year (All Features / STA-UKAN)	1.217	1.586	-0.303	1.587	2.061	-0.069	1.741	2.268	-0.349	1.742	2.274	-0.222

Note: Seasonal Mean is the unweighted average of the four season-specific models. For MBE, averaging indicates the overall bias tendency across seasonal models.

S13 Meteorological Predictors

Table S9 lists the 17 atmospheric predictor types used throughout the study. Each variable is available from both the CMA and ECMWF reforecast systems, so the final multisource predictor stack preserves the same physical-variable definition across the two forecast sources.

Table S9: Meteorological predictor variables and their vertical levels. The predictor set contains 17 variable types: five near-surface variables, six variables at 850 hPa, and the same six variables at 250 hPa. Each variable is available from both CMA and ECMWF reforecasts.

Index	Vertical level	Predictor variable	Abbreviation (unit)
1	Near surface	2-m air temperature	T_{2m} (K)
2	Near surface	2-m dew-point temperature	Td_{2m} (K)
3	Near surface	Surface pressure	sp (Pa)
4	Near surface	10-m zonal wind	u_{10} (m s ⁻¹)
5	Near surface	10-m meridional wind	v_{10} (m s ⁻¹)
6	850 hPa	Air temperature	t_{850} (K)
7	850 hPa	Zonal wind	u_{850} (m s ⁻¹)
8	850 hPa	Meridional wind	v_{850} (m s ⁻¹)
9	850 hPa	Specific humidity	q_{850} (kg kg ⁻¹)
10	850 hPa	Vertical velocity	w_{850} (Pa s ⁻¹)
11	850 hPa	Geopotential height	z_{850} (gpm)
12	250 hPa	Air temperature	t_{250} (K)
13	250 hPa	Zonal wind	u_{250} (m s ⁻¹)
14	250 hPa	Meridional wind	v_{250} (m s ⁻¹)
15	250 hPa	Specific humidity	q_{250} (kg kg ⁻¹)
16	250 hPa	Vertical velocity	w_{250} (Pa s ⁻¹)
17	250 hPa	Geopotential height	z_{250} (gpm)

Each predictor is ingested from both CMA and ECMWF reforecasts; source membership is therefore identical for all 17 variable types.